

Project Number: S1099

Project Title: Phosphorus dynamics in agroecosystems

Requested Project Duration: From October 1, 2025 to September 30, 2030

Non-Technical Summary: Phosphorus (P) is a primary nutrient source in agriculture. From the 40 Megatons of P per year which is mined for US agriculture, more than 70% of the useable material is used for production of fertilizers. Many efforts are underway to recover P from natural ecosystems and use as fertilizer input, often referred to a "bio-mining". **The goal of this Multistate project is to illuminate phosphorus dynamics and highlight opportunities in development of technologies for recovery and reuse of phosphorus in agricultural systems.** The research objectives for reaching this goal are:

- Develop database for technologies relevant to agricultural P management;
- Document current and emerging technologies for P monitoring;
- Increase understanding of P impacts on ecosystems; and
- Investigate the history of P management in the United States.

The target audience for this project is: growers, technology developers, resource managers, extension programs, and researchers working in areas relevant to natural resource management. The outcomes will be curated in our Multistate database, and are designed to benefit as follows:

- New database accessible to stakeholders and technology end-users;
- Increased research reproducibility via shared protocols on technology development;
- Information for clarifying fundamental concepts in P management;
- Information on challenges/opportunities related to P management such as recovery from non-traditional sources; and
- Information on natural resource management for use at public museums.

Our team is working with partners and other organizations to maximize the dissemination and sharing of the outputs/outcomes from this group. We have developed three sub-committee groups which will identify key activities and work to achieve the outcomes. Each year, we will host a meeting to facilitate convergence of the outcomes produced by sub-committees using best practices in team science.